

Impact of Breed and Feed Restriction on Growth and Development of Pre-Lay Characteristics of Isa Brown and Lohmann Brown Pullets

Jaiyeoba, B.B^{1*} & Oluyomi, B.A²

^{1,2}Bioresources Development Center Idofin, National Biotechnology Research and Development Agency, Nigeria

* Corresponding Author: Bidemi Jaiyeoba1, Email: bidemi.jaiyeoba@nbrda.gov.ng

APA citation: Jaiyeoba, B., & Oluyomi, B. (2025). Impact of Breed and Feed Restriction on Growth and development of Pre-Lay Characteristics of Isa Brown and Lohmann Brown Pullets. *JENER Journal of Empirical and Non-Empirical Research*, 5(3), 89-91

ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 27 August 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Breeds Feed Restriction Body Weight <i>ad-libitum</i></p>	<p>The study aimed to assess how different breeds and feed restriction practices influence the growth and pre-lay characteristics of Isa Brown and Lohmann Brown pullet chickens during their rearing phase. A total of 360 day-old chicks, 180 from each breed, were raised on standard starter diets until eight weeks old, followed by three Different feed restriction levels from 9 to 22 weeks of (i) <i>ad-libitum</i>, (ii) 90% of <i>ad-lib</i> feed allocation and (iii) 80% of <i>ad-lib</i> feed allocation, in a 2 X 3 factorial design). The study found that breed did not significantly impact body weight, feed intake or egg weight but age at sexual maturity was slightly delayed ($P < 0.05$) in Isa Brown. Feed restriction did not affect ($P > 0.05$) feed intake or body weight but pullets on 80% restriction showed higher ($P < 0.05$) egg weight and age at sexual maturity</p>

1. Introduction

The poultry industry faces challenges due to high feed costs, which account for a significant portion (60-70%) of production expenses (Wilson and Bayer, 2000). Efficient feed utilization is crucial for maximizing profitability (Al-Taleb, 2007). Feed restriction during the growing phase can improve feed efficiency and reduce costs (Bruggeman et al., 2005; Mbugua et al., 1985). This study aimed to explore the effects of different feed management practices on growth and development of pullet chicken.

2. Materials and Methodology

2.2 Experimental Site

The study was carried out at the Teaching and Research farm of Livestock Division, Bioresources Development Center, Idofin, National Biotechnology Research and Development Agency, Nigeria. The Center is located within Yagba-East Local Government Area of Kogi state, in the rain forest zone of North Central Nigeria. It is located on latitude 8.2625°N, longitude 5.7154°E, with 321 square kilometers of area. It is an undulating upland zone with an altitude of 250m above sea level; characterized by metamorphic rocks consisting of sidestepped outcrops either singly or in a group.

2.3 Climate And Vegetation

The state falls under tropical climate with two seasons: rainy season which starts from March to November and a dry season which starts from November to March. Temperature ranges from 21°C to 35°C with high relative humidity. Rainfall ranges from 1350 to 1778mm. The northeast trade wind and the south-westerly wind blow during the dry and rainy season respectively. To the north is savannah and the south is a tropical forest in Kogi state.

2.4 Experimental Animals And Management

Experimental animals consist of 360-day old chicks (DOC), 180 each of Lohmann Brown and Isa Brown strains. The day old chicks, hatched on the same day were obtained from Olam hatchery, Kaduna and Amo-Sanders hatchery, Ibadan, Nigeria. Upon receipt, birds were inspected, tagged and brooded separately in three-tier chick cages (80 x 70 x 25 cm) up to eight weeks. Birds were vaccinated against common diseases associated with pullets in Nigeria. Chicks of each strain were randomly grouped into twelve replicates comprising of fifteen birds. Birds were weighed from week 9 up to twenty three weeks of age, placed on a standard chick-feed (ME, 2681 kcal; CP, 21%). Between 9 to 23 weeks, 180 chicks from each strain were randomly assigned to 18 cage pens (50 x 46 x 46 cm) comprising 10 chicks per pen in replicates of six which were randomly placed into upper, middle and lower levels and were placed on standard grower feed containing ME,

2534 kcal and CP, 18%, during which birds within each strain were divided into three treatments corresponding to three feeding regimes which

include i) Control group (100% feed allowance based on body weight), ii) 90% restricted feed; and iii) 80% restricted feed (Table 1). The feed provided during the grower stage was 8% of body weight.

Table 1: Feeding plan

Age(weeks)	Control 100% feed	10% Restriction of feed	20% Restriction of feed
DOC to 8 weeks	<i>ad-libitum</i>	<i>ad-libitum</i>	<i>ad-libitum</i>
9-22	8% of body weight	Less 10% full feeding	Less 20% full feeding
	Full feeding		

2.5 Experimental Design

The experimental design was a completely randomized design with a 2 x 3 factorial arrangement.

2.6 Statistical Model

$$Y_{ijkl} = \mu + \alpha_i + \beta_j + \alpha\beta_{ij} + E_{ijkl}$$

Where:

Y_{ijkl} = the mean observation

μ = the general mean

α_i = the i th effect of breed

β_j = the j th effect of feed restriction

$\alpha\beta_{ij}$ = the interaction effects of the i th breed and the j th feed restriction

E_{ijkl} = the random error term

2.7 Data Collection

Bodyweight of birds was collected at 9 to 23 weeks of age using Camry digital scale to monitor weight gain. Feed consumption, feed conversion ratio and age at onset of laying as well as egg production record were monitored. Other parameters measured include weight at the point of lay. Other data were computed at the end of the experiment using the formulae below:

$$(i) \text{ Feed conversion ratio} = \frac{\text{Feeds intake (g)/bird/week}}{\text{Average weight (g)/bird/week}}$$

$$(ii) \text{ Feed intake} = \frac{\text{Total feed intake per bird(g) during experiment}}{\text{per bird per day} \times \text{Total number of days of the experiment}}$$

$$(iii) \text{ Cost of feed consumed per day} = \frac{\text{Quantity of feed consumed/bird/day}}{\text{Cost per kilogram of feed type}}$$

RESEARCH ARTICLE

2.8 Statistical Analysis

Data obtained were subjected to the General linear model analysis of SAS software (1999). Means were separated using Tukey's Honest significant

test at 5% level of significance to establish any effect of breed and feed restriction factors on the performance of the animals.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Effects of breed on growth performance of pullet

Table 2: Effect of breed on growth performance of pullets (9 to 22 weeks).

Parameters	Breed			SEM
	Lohmann brown	Isa brown		
Initial weight (g)(9 weeks)	805 ^a	781 ^b		0.005
Final weight (g)(22 weeks)	1697	1683		0.021
Weight gain (g)	863	873		22.96
Feed intake/bird (kg)	8.15	8.13		3.068
Feed conversion ratio	20.75	19.96		0.59
Feed intake/bird/day (g)	80.69	80.52		0.00
Cost of daily feed intake (N)	9.73	9.71		0.00
Bodyweight at point of lay (g)	1711	1738		20.19
Egg weight at point of lay (g)	45.88	45.75		0.87
Age at point of lay(days)	152.44 ^b	157 ^a		1.79

SEM= Standard error of means; abc-means with different superscripts along the same row are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

The effects of breed on the growth performance of pullets are presented in table 2. Significant difference were observed for body weight at nine weeks when feed restriction commenced which are attributes of breed differences while no difference were observed for body weight and weight gain at 22 weeks of age which indicates similarity in genetic makeup for growth of the breeds. These observations were similar to the reports of Olawumi (2011) and Sarica et al (2009) who attributed these observations to different genetic potentials for growth at different ages. No significant difference were observed for total feed intake per bird, feed conversion ratio, daily feed intake per bird and daily cost of feed per bird which could be attributed to similarity of genetic potentials of both breeds in utilizing

feed. This in contradiction to the reports of Sarica et al (2009) which indicated otherwise. Point of lay characteristics were significant for age at sexual maturity while no difference were observed for body weight and egg weight at sexual maturity. Sexual maturity is a function of both genotype and body weight of birds with heavier body weight birds maturing earlier than lighter ones. This is in line with earlier reports of Taha et al (2010) and Olawumi (2011). They further concluded that egg weight at sexual maturity is determine by genotype and body weight at sexual maturity.

3.2 Effects of feed restriction on growth performance of pullet

Table 3: Effect of feed restriction on growth performance of pullets (9-22 weeks)

Parameters	Feed restriction			SEM
	Full-fed	90% feed	80% feed	
Initial weight(g)	793	789	797	0.006
Final weight(g)	1718 ^a	1685 ^b	1666 ^c	0.026
Weight gain(g)	903 ^a	868 ^b	833 ^b	28.15
Feed intake/bird(kg)	9.094	8.16	7.17	0.00
Feed conversion ratio	19.95	20.88	20.23	0.720
Feed intake/bird/day(g)	90.04	80.80	70.98	0.00
Cost of daily feed intake(N)	10.85	9.74	8.56	0.00
Bodyweight at point of lay(g)	1736	1697	1740	24.74
Egg weight at point of lay(g)	43.14 ^c	46.06 ^b	48.24 ^a	1.066
Age at sexual maturity(days)	152.08 ^b	153.50 ^b	159 ^a	2.179

SEM= Standard error of means; abc-means with different superscripts along the same row are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

The effect of feed restriction on growth performance of pullets was presented in Table 3. No significance were observed for total feed intake per bird, feed conversion ratio, feed intake per bird per day, daily cost of feed intake per bird and age at sexual maturity which could be due to better feed utilization by birds on feed restriction than their counterparts on ad-libitum feed. This observations were in line with the reports of Tesfaye et al (2009) but contrary to that of Sarica et al (2009) and Chiemella et al (2015). Body weight at sexual maturity observed in this study which was not significant indicates that feed restriction program

during rearing have no effect on body weight at sexual maturity. This finding was in agreement with the reports of Sarica et al (2009) and Tesfaye et al (2009). Significant difference were also observed for body weight change, egg weight at sexual maturity and age at sexual maturity. Tesfaye et al (2009) and Sarica et al (2009) attributed delay in attainment of sexual maturity to distribution of available energy to different organs to make priority for tissue growth resulting in large egg follicles, egg weight and body weight.

3.3 Effects of breed and feed restriction on growth performance of pullet

Table 4: Interactive effect of breed and feed restriction on growth performance of pullets (9-22 weeks)

Parameters	Breed						SEM
	Lohmann Brown			Isa Brown			
	Full fed	90% feed	80% feed	Full fed	90% feed	80% feed	
Initial wt. (g)	803	794	819	785	783	776	0.008
Final wt. (g)	1779 ^a	1645 ^f	1666 ^c	1657 ^e	1726 ^b	1665 ^d	0.037
Wt. gain (g)	949 ^a	807 ^b	834 ^b	857 ^b	930 ^a	833 ^b	39.74
FI/bird (kg)	9.11	8.09	7.25	9.08	8.23	7.09	0.00
FCR	19.47 ^b	22.37 ^a	20.41 ^b	20.43 ^b	19.40 ^b	20.05 ^b	1.02
FI/bird/day (g)	90.19	80.13	71.74	89.88	81.46	70.21	0.00
COD FI (N)	10.87	9.66	8.65	10.84	9.82	8.46	0.00
B wt.at *SM(g)	1773 ^a	1697 ^b	1726 ^b	1698 ^b	1762 ^a	1753 ^a	34.94
Egg wt. at SM(g)	43.71 ^b	47.76 ^a	46.17 ^{ab}	42.57 ^b	44.36 ^{ab}	49.92 ^a	1.506
Age at SM(days)	150 ^b	151.17 ^b	156.17 ^b	154.17 ^b	155.83 ^b	162.50 ^a	3.078

SEM, Standard error of means; abc, means with different superscripts along the same row are significantly different ($p < 0.05$). *SM, sexual maturity; FI, feed intake; B wt, body weight; wt, weight; FCR, feed conversion ratio; COD, cost of daily.

RESEARCH ARTICLE

The effects of breed and feed restriction on growth performance of pullet are presented in Table 4. No statistical difference were observed for total feed intake per bird, daily feed intake per bird daily cost of feed intake per bird indicating that strains of same breed respond similarly to different feed restriction programs. Results from this study were similarly reported by Saleh *et al* (1994) and Sarica *et al* (2009). The significant difference observed in this study for body weight at 22 weeks of age shows broader breed differences and indicates that different breeds responds differently to feed restriction programs. The significance observed for body weight at sexual maturity for both breeds indicates that different breeds responded differently to feed restriction. Same observations were reported by Saleh *et al* and Sarica *et al* (2009). Feed conversion ratio was significantly higher 90% feed restriction in Lohmann Brown pullets while others were similar indicating that different breeds respond similarly to same feed restriction programs. Age at sexual maturity, egg weight at sexual maturity and body weight at sexual maturity values indicates that different feed restriction programs on different breeds did not have a definite pattern. This report was in agreement with earlier reports by Saleh *et al* (1994).

4. Conclusion

1. Both Isa Brown and Isa Brown used in this study showed that 20% feed restriction group had similar performance as full fed groups, showing that feed restriction up to 20% would not adversely affect growth performance and age at sexual maturity.
2. Both Isa Brown and Lohmann Brown responded similarly to Total feed intake per bird and cost of daily feed intake per bird but differently to body weight at sexual maturity, egg weight at sexual maturity, age at sexual maturity and body weight changes.

Funding sources:

This study did not receive any grant from funding agencies.

Declaration of authors' conflict of interest:

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

References

- Al-Taleb S. 2007. Effect of nutrient intake restrictions by dietary dilutions with sand on broiler performance. *Jordan Journal of Agriculture Science*, 3: 281-287.
- Baloch WA, Suzuki H, Onoue Y (2001). Effect of different fasting and feeding regimes on body weight and productive performance of layers after first induced molt. *Pakistan J. Zool.* 32 (3):275-277.
- Chiemela, P.N., Onyeagu, C.E. and Egbu C. F. (2015). Effect of feed restriction on growth performance characteristics of broiler chickens. *Elixir Agriculture*, 88:36354-36357.
- Gous, R.M., Bradford, G.D., Johnston, S.A. and Morris, T.R. 2000. Effect of age of release from light and food restriction on age at sexual maturity and egg production of laying pullets. *British poultry science*, 41:263-271.
- Hurwitz, S. and Plavink, I. (1989). Severe feed restriction in pullets during the early growing period: Performance and relationship among age, body weight and egg weight at the onset of production. *Poultry Science*. 68:914-924.
- Kim, S.H., Lee, S.J., Jang, B.G., Choi, C.H. & Ryu, K.S. 2004. Effects of restricted feeding to pullet on weight and composition of body, laying performance, egg quality and endocrine in brown layers. *Proceedings of XXII World's Poultry Congress*, June 8-13, Istanbul, Turkey, pp: 387-387
- Leeson, S. and Summers, J. (2001). Scoot's Nutrition of the Chicken. *University Book. Guelph, Canada*.
- Leeson, S., Caston, L. and Summers, J. (1997). Layer performance of four strains of Leghorn pullets subjected to various rearing programs. *Poultry science*, 76: 1-5.
- Maaza, S. (1981). *Comparative laboratory and animal evaluation and estimation of nutritive values of Noug and peanut seed cake*. MSc. Thesis.
- Mbugua, P.N., Austic, R.E. and Cunningham, D.L. (1985). Effects of Feed Restriction on Growth and Metabolism of Replacement Pullets. *Poultry Science*. 64:1950-1958.
- Olawumi, S.O. (2011): Study On Pre-Lay Characteristics Of Three Breeds Of Commercial Layers In The Derived Savannah Zone Of Nigeria, *Pakistan Journal of Biological Sciences* 14(23):1061-1065, 2001
- Onagbesan, O., Bruggeman, V., De Smit, L., Debonne, M., Witters, A., Tona, K., Everaert, N. & Decuypere, E. (2007). Gas exchange during storage and incubation of avian eggs: effects on embryogenesis, hatchability, chick quality and post-hatch growth. *World's Poultry Science Journal*, 63, 557-559.
- Sahota, A. W. and Bhatti, B.M. (2001). Effect of feed restriction during growing period on laying performance of white leghorn hens. *Pakistan Veterinary Journal*. 21 (3):145-147.
- Saleh. K., Attia, Y.A. and Younis, H. (1996): Effect of feed restriction and breed on compensatory growth, abdominal fat and some production traits of broiler chicks. *Arch. Getflugelk.* 1996. 60(4):153-159, ISSN 0003-9088.
- Sarica, M Yamak, B. and Yamak, U.S. (2009). The Effects of Feed Restrictions in Rearing Period on Growth and Laying Performances of White and Brown Layer Hybrids in Different adult Body Weights. *Asian Journal of Poultry Science*. 3(2):30-41.
- SAS (1999). *SAS Users Guide: Statistics*, Version 9.1. SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC.
- Taha, A.E., Abd El-ghany, F.A. and Sharaf, M.M. (2010). Strain and Sex effects on productive and slaughter performance of developed local Egyptian and Canadian chicken strains. *Egyptian Poultry Science*, 30:1059-1072.
- Tesfaye, E., Berhan, T., Aynalem, H., and Tadelie, D. (2009). Effects of feed restriction on production and reproductive performance of Rhode Island Red Pullets. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*. 4(7): 642-648.
- Tolkamp, B.J., Sandilands, V. and Kyriazakis, I. (2005): Effects of Qualitative Feed Restriction during Rearing on the performance of Broilers during Rearing and Lay. *Poultry science*. 84:1286-1293.
- Vakili, R. and Akbaroglu, F. 2006: Effect of feed restriction method during rearing on growth and blood indices of stress in broiler breeder. *Proceedings of XII European Poultry Conference*, 2006, *World Poultry Science Journal, Italy*: 382-382.
- Van Marle- Köster E and N.H. Casey. 2001. Phenotypic characterization of native chicken lines in South Africa. *Animal Genetic Resources Information* 29: 71-78. *World Poultry Science* 64: 53-64.
- Wilson, K. J. & Beyer, R. S. (2000). Poultry nutrition information for the small flock. *World Poultry Science* 64:53-64

Publish in JENER Journal, <https://jenerjournal.com>